

Principals' Leadership Impact on School Climate in Private High Schools in Istanbul

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Abstract

Leadership is a broad and comprehensive concept that is associated with a variety of styles and theories, including Transactional and Transformational Leadership (Vecchio et al., 2008), Learning-Centred Leadership (Southworth, 2009), and Emotional Intelligence (Goldring et al., 2015), and others. In theory, there is still an opportunity for more comparisons and links between different types of leadership (Ricard et al., 2017). This research aimed to investigate the extent and nature of the link between principal leadership and School Climate. This research focused on determining the level of leadership, and school climate of a private high school in Istanbul Turkey, in addition assessing the relationship between leadership and school climate, hence developing the differences in the level of leadership and school climate based on demography and determining the dimensions that contributes to the Principals' Leadership. The results of this study appear to meet the targeted objective by investigating the level of Leadership and Level of School Climate, bringing the actual relationship between both variables, and finding out if there is any significant and differences

Keywords: Leadership, school climate, students

INTRODUCTION

This research aimed to investigate the extent and nature of the link between principal leadership and School Climate. This study offers a systematic review, and multivariate meta-analysis of the empirical literature on the impacts of principal leadership on School Climate generated between 2010 and 2020. Thus, this study is significant because it (a) investigated how principals' leadership influenced School Climate, (b) revealed how collective decisions made by principals and administrators influence learning conditions, and (c) identified functions within leadership that principals can use, school leaders, district administrators, and instructors to impact the school climate and process. The goal of this study was addressed using a collective case study technique. This methodology provides for a thorough investigation of the effects of principal leadership on School Climate. For a collective case study method, research questions should strive to address how or why questions (Yin, 2018). To that goal, the following research issues were addressed in this study:

- 1) what is the level of School Climate,
 - 2) what is the level of level of Leadership
 - 3) what is the relationship between Leadership and School Climate
 - 4) What is the differences in the level of leadership, and level school climate based on demography,
 - 5) What are factors affecting relationship between Leadership and School Climate
- Leadership "increases the school's potential for boosting teachers' instructional capacity" (Heck & Hallinger, 2014, p. 658). According to Goddard et al. (2015), principals' instructional leadership may help teachers improve teaching, and leadership and teacher collaboration may

contribute to school effectiveness by increasing collective efficacy. In contrast, the absence of specific criteria in the context of the Instructional Leadership concept leads to a misunderstanding of leadership. Duke (1982), Rowan, Bossert, and Dwyer (1983), Hallinger and Murphy (1985), Murphy (1988), and Purkey and Smith (1990) are some of the authors (1983). Principals are frequently caught up in managerial practices that prevent them from attaining their full potential as Instructional Leaders. According to Barnes et al. (2010), "principals must transform their actions from a management to an instructional focus" (p.273). Principals must demonstrate leadership by infusing leadership techniques into their position and character; otherwise, their job will provide an administrative persona that may fit into an administrative domain. Transformational leadership is a practical kind of school administration leadership. It makes an enormous contribution to changing individuals into future leaders by giving them control over their behaviours and personality traits. Individuals must raise knowledge and enhance their abilities to adopt leadership roles and accomplish their work obligations in a well-organized way. However School climate refers to school attributes in which there is a constant interaction of various variables such as student-teacher relationships, teaching and learning processes, qualities, approaches, and practices (Thapa et al., 2013). Researchers have devised many definitions of school climate, which continue to confuse (Thapa et al., 2013). The synthesis of human interaction occurs at various levels: microsystem (immediate environment), mesosystem (school, outside environment), exosystem (social

and cultural values), macrosystem (social and cultural values), and chronosystem (changes over time) (Bronfenbrenner, 1992). As a result, we can better understand how the school and its relational dynamics affect student outcomes in various areas of life. The quality and character of school life are defined as the school climate (Cohen et al., 2009, p. 182). Decades and decades of research have revealed that the nature of school climate is multidimensional in and of itself. The school climate can influence the learning environment in both positive and negative ways (Freiberg, 1998). Kuperminc, Leadbeater, Emmons, and Blatt (1997) discovered that students in a positive school climate had fewer behavioural and emotional problems. School climate is not static; it is highly dynamic, and it is necessary to pay attention to this dynamicity (Hoy & Hoy, 2003). Articulation of dynamic aspects of education has been studied for over a century. Similarly, the climate of an organization defines it (Halpin & Croft, 1963). According to Halpin and Croft's research, school climate can be classified as open, autonomous, controlled, familiar, paternal, or closed (Halpin & Croft, 1963). Achievement gap and dropout among students remain critical concerns for teachers, guidance counsellors, educationists, and educational planners, particularly in India, due to heavy investment in education (Sharma, 1982). The dynamics of teaching-learning, its paradoxes, and its process are vital, if not essential, for bringing about a qualitative change in the field of education. The transaction in the classroom settings elegantly changes the fabric of the student's existence, laying the groundwork for limitless possibilities. The primary goal of this study work is to gain knowledge of leadership positions

in educational institutions and how leadership affects School Climate. There is a significant link between student learning and leadership performance; in certain circumstances, educators and school personnel are seen as the leaders in whose hands the educational requirements, developmental features, norms, rules, laws, policies, and procedures are vested. There is a significant association between all of these factors and the learning that pupils do in schools. It all comes down to commitment and dedication to a robust and comprehensive leadership support system that aims to strengthen the link between learning and leadership by defining what leaders should know, be aware of, and be able to do by providing them with the tools and feedback needed to improve and, ultimately, excel (Mezzacappa, 2008). The main goal of leaders, the school, and the educators is for the students to learn and perform well within the school. For this purpose, they are taught all of the necessary aspects such as discipline, obedience, control, motivation, dedication, and how to put in all of the hard work to give their best. In order to achieve intended goals, both leaders and students must demonstrate initiative and a sense of creativity. As ideas about school leadership have increasingly emphasized learning and school improvement, leadership assessment has emphasized leaders' performance and results rather than qualities and characteristics. It aimed at determining how well leaders and their performance meet criteria defined by professional bodies and policy; served influential and cumulative purposes, often aiming at leaders' learning and further development; (Mezzacappa, 2008). Leaders of reputable schools devote themselves to the formulation, articulation, execution, and care of a shared and endorsed vision for learning

by the school community. A knowledge-based curriculum has been developed, and it has been expressed as follows: (Murphy, 2007). Vision for learning includes creating, expressing, putting vision into action, and stewarding vision. This concept comprises instructional time, knowledge and engagement, hiring and distributing employees, and supporting staff. The curricular Program includes knowledge, participation, expectations, standards, learning opportunities, and curriculum alignment. The assessment Program includes knowledge and involvement, assessment techniques, curriculum and communication, and data utilization. Professional development, communities of professional practice, and community-anchored schools are all examples of Communities of Learning. Resource Acquisition and Use — This includes obtaining, allocating, and utilizing resources. Organizational Culture - This includes emphasising production, the learning environment, the customized environment, and continual development. Stakeholder participation, diversity, environmental context, and ethics are examples of social advocacy. The research in this study can be described as both exploratory and descriptive. In the beginning, exploratory research was carried out since little comprehension of the problem domain existed. In order to raise awareness about Leadership and its impact on School Climate, a large amount of literature concerning theories related to the problem area was examined.

Based on the findings of the study, all the mean scores were above 3; it means that the Teachers in private high school in Istanbul (case of study) have positive perceptions of principals' leadership and teachers' exceptions met in the execution of the services. Furthermore, four

factors, namely Belonging, Safety, Trust, Achievement were identified in the Leadership scale. Because this research was investigating the level of leadership and school climate of Teachers, the findings shows that the level of all four leadership dimensions were high from the perspective of respondents. The lowest level of leadership dimensions is Achievement, followed by Belonging, Safety and Trust. Furthermore, the outcomes of this study showed that the level of leadership was high. Finally, the findings indicated that the level of school climate was also high meaning that the teachers were satisfied with environment delivered by the AIS principals. Based on the findings, all dimensions showed a significant relationship with the school climate. This finding supports the study by Dore (2021) who said that the most important dimension affecting Leadership and create a positive school climate is Trust, Belonging and safety.

REFERENCES

- Harrison, L. 2011. Transformational Leadership, Integrity, and Power. ERIC Number: EJ946442. ISSN-0164-7970.
- Mezzacappa, 2008. Published in Educational Leadership Review: Portland Conference Special Edition, pp. 5-16, October 2011. Used by permission. Original version can be found at <http://cnx.org/content/m41081/latest/?collection=col11362/latest>.
- Day, C., Sammons, P., Leithwood, K., Hopkins, D., Gu, Q. Brown, E., with Ahtaridou, E. 2011. Successful School Leadership: Linking with Learning and Achievement. Maidenhead: McGraw Hill Open University Press. (Murphy, 2007, p.182)
- Witziers, B., Bosker, R., & Krüger, M. 2003. Educational leadership and student achievement: The elusive search for

- an association. *Educational Administration Quarterly*, 39 (3): 398-425.
- Halpin, A. W., Croft, D. B. 1963. *The Organizational Climate of Schools*. Chicago, IL: Midwest Administration Center of the University of Chicago. (Sharma, 1982).
- A Review of School Climate Research
Amrit Thapa, Jonathan Cohen, Shawn Guffey, Ann Higgins-D'Alessandro
- Hoy, A.W., Hoy, W. K. (2003). *Instructional leadership: A learning-centered guide*. Allyn & Bacon. (Freiberg, 1998).
- Bronfenbrenner, U. 1992. Ecological systems theory. In R. Vasta (Ed.), *Six theories of child development: Revised formulations and current issues* (pp. 187–249). Jessica Kingsley Publishers.
- Hallinger, P. and Murphy, J. (1985) *Assessing the Instructional Management Behaviour of Principals*. *The Elementary School Journal*, 86: 217-247.
- Murphy, R. 1988. *Social Closure: The Theory of Monopolization and Exclusion*. New York: Oxford University Press. Research on Effective Schools: A Cautionary Note
- Brian Rowan, Steven T. Bossert, David C. Dwyer
First Published April 1, 1983 Research Article
- Yin, R. K. 2018. *Case Study Research and Applications: Design and Methods* (6th ed.). Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage.
- Heck, R.H., Hallinger, P. 2014. Modeling the longitudinal effects of school leadership on teaching and learning. *Journal of Education Administration*, 52: 653-681.
- The relationship between growth in principal leadership and growth in school performance: The teacher perspective Author links open overlay panel
Jianping Shen^aXin Ma^bNancy Mansberger^aHuang Wu^aLouann A. BierleinPalmer^aSue Poppink^aPatricia L. Reeves^a
- A Review of School Climate Research
Amrit Thapa, Jonathan Cohen, Shawn Guffey, , Ann Higgins-D'Alessandro